

On the Utilization of Radial Vibration Transient Signals for Induction Machine Misalignment Diagnosis

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Jose E. Ruiz-Sarrio

Instituto Tecnológico de la Energía (ITE) Instituto Tecnológico de la Energía (ITE)
Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)
Valencia, Spain

jorduisar@die.upv.es

Vicente Biot-Monterde

Valencia, Spain

vibiomon@die.upv.es

Carlos Madariaga-Cifuentes

Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Concepción
Concepción, Chile

carlosmadariaga@udec.cl

Angela Navarro-Navarro

Instituto Tecnológico de la Energía (ITE)
Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)
Valencia, Spain

annana3@die.upv.es

Jose A. Antonino-Daviu

Instituto Tecnológico de la Energía (ITE)
Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV)
Valencia, Spain

joanda@die.upv.es

Abstract—Vibration measurement is widely employed for diagnosing malfunctions in rotating machinery including electrical machines. While steady-state vibration signals are extensively studied for diagnosing mechanical defects such as misalignment, load unbalances, and bearing defects, transient analysis of vibration signals remains a research gap. In particular, vibration measurement in the housing of electrical machines offers insights into both mechanical and electromagnetic signatures. This manuscript aims to explore the potential of transient radial vibration analysis to enhance the reliability of misalignment diagnosis. To this aim, a squirrel cage induction machine is utilized as a case study, while transient vibrations under slip swinging conditions such as soft-started and directly-fed start-ups are analysed. The analysis of slowly varying transient vibrations reveals severe misalignment indications that cannot be adequately addressed using steady-state current or vibration spectra. This is particularly interesting for machines with intermittent duty and frequent starts (e.g., conveyors, pumps, fans, etc.).

Index Terms—component, formatting, style, styling, insert

I. INTRODUCTION

Rotating electrical machine diagnosis and monitoring requires multidisciplinary knowledge including electromagnetic and pure mechanical phenomena. Vibration signal monitoring continues to be a widespread methodology due to the high amount of standards based on this physical magnitude and its superiority to diagnose mechanical faults [1]. Nevertheless, alternative methodologies such as phase current monitoring

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or stray-flux represents a valid alternative when vibration acquisition is not available [2].

Machine misalignment and mass unbalance represent a common case of mechanical defect that heavily impacts the machine performance and reliability. The detection, discrimination and severity quantification of such defects attracts significant research attention [3]. Induction machine misalignment via vibration and current signals during steady state operation is broadly researched in works such as [4]–[6]. However, the analysis of transient current and vibrations to elucidate misalignment faults is scarcely addressed in literature [7], [8]. The transient analysis of vibration signals of induction machines presents potential to address misalignment root locus and severity. This stems from the combination of mechanical and electromagnetic signatures contained in housing vibration signals.

The present paper introduces the analysis of transient vibration signals to aid on the misalignment fault diagnosis in induction machines. The study is performed in a laboratory environment by analysing transient evolutions during slip swing start-up conditions (i.e., directly-fed and soft-started motor). In addition, transient radial vibration signatures are thoroughly and comprehensively analysed. Phase current signals are studied alongside vibrations to enhance the comprehensibility of the phenomena. The present manuscript is organized as follows. Section II poses the main theoretical concepts behind radial vibration signature and shaft misalignment defects. Section III describes the experimental test bench and the performed experiments. Section IV thoroughly analyses the current and vibration signatures during both considered start-up modes. Section V presents the analysis of the misalignment

fault considering well-known steady-state indicators and the proposed analysis of transient evolutions. Section VI poses the main conclusions of the work.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Vibration signature of induction machines

The vibration phenomena in electrical machines possess a well-known multi-physical nature. Structures (i.e., stator, rotor, and auxiliary elements) are excited by forces of diverse origin. Each structural element possess an inherent frequency behaviour depending on parameters such as stiffness, mass and damping. Thus, forces attenuate or amplify depending on the vibrating transfer path [9].

In the field of electrical machines, the exciting forces possess diverse nature. Radial electromagnetic forces origin in the airgap and excite the stator structure. The magnitude of these forces scales linearly with the square of the airgap radial flux density (i.e., $F_r \propto b_r^2$), thereby dependent upon the airgap permeance, as well as the stator and rotor magnetomotive forces. Electromagnetic torque oscillations result from forward and backward propagating waves when electromagnetic unbalances occur. These oscillations are superimposed to the main torque component and contribute to the machine vibration [10]. Other electromagnetic phenomena affecting vibrations are magnetostriction, standstill locking and unbalance magnetic pull [11]. Vibrations of pure mechanical nature are induced within the machine itself and in auxiliary systems. Examples of this kind are bearing, rotor/coupling unbalance, load induced vibrations, etc. [12]. In addition, impacts and unwanted contacts due to malfunction also affect the vibration spectrum significantly [13].

B. Misalignment fault description and interpretation

The misalignment defect refers to the misplacement of the rotational axis between two rotating shafts, which may stem from internal factors like bearing misalignment or external influences such as those imposed by the driven load [14]. Figure 1 shows the different types of misalignment in both horizontal and vertical planes. Pure misalignment is not commonly found in real applications since perfect alignment is not practically feasible. Nevertheless, mixed misalignment can show prominent angular or parallel features.

Misalignment fault is strongly related to airgap eccentricity in the context of rotating electrical machines. Traditionally, misalignment is linked to static eccentricity cases [4]. Nevertheless, in a practical scenario inherent mass unbalances, stator ovality, or bearing misplacement are present. Therefore, the misalignment can be understood as a mixed eccentricity case study and eccentricity fault indicators are feasible for diagnosis purposes.

III. TEST BENCH AND EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

The machine specimen under test is a 4 pole, 1.1 kW, squirrel cage induction machine. Table I shows the main characteristics of the machine under study. The studied machine specimen is mechanically coupled to a DC generator

Fig. 1. Misalignment description where ⊙ represent parallel misalignment axis and ⊚ represent angular misalignment axis, (a) horizontal plane, (b) vertical plane

via flexible coupling. The generator is electrically coupled to resistive loads for energy dissipation, and the resistant torque is controlled by adjusting the DC field intensity. The vibration signals are acquired in the drive end of the machine in radial direction. Two accelerometers (PCB352C33) are placed at 12 o'clock and 3 o'clock positions. The accelerometers are coupled to a signal conditioning unit connected to the acquisition system. A wave recorder with four channels is utilized to synchronously sample the two vibration outputs, phase-to-ground voltage, and phase current at 20 kHz sampling frequency. Figure 2 shows details about the test-bench in the physical environment.

TABLE I
INDUCTION MOTOR CHARACTERISTICS

Number of poles	4
Rated power	1.1 kW
Rated speed	1440 rpm
Power factor	0.78
Rated voltage	230/400 V
Number of rotor bars	28
Number of stator slots	36

The signals are acquired during the machine start-up in two

Fig. 2. Experimental test bench for the machine under study and acquisition system description

Fig. 3. Soft-starter equivalent circuit

different excitation modes. Both of them impose a slip swing ranging from unity to close to zero slip, depending on the operating condition. The directly-fed mode is defined by the grid supply at 400 V line-to-line voltage at 50 Hz. However, the start-up at nominal voltage provides a very fast start, where transient evolutions are not observed. For this reason, the analysis is performed for a 60% nominal voltage directly-fed start-up. The second mode utilizes a soft-starting method based on thyristor bridges for two of the motor phases. The firing angle of the thyristors is controlled to start the machine in approximately 20 seconds with an start voltage of 40% the nominal value. This methodology provides a progressive motor start and avoids high current peaks. Figure 3 shows the equivalent circuit and control logic of the utilized soft-starter device (i.e., ABB PSR3-600-70).

The studied misalignment is implemented in the xz vertical plane according to figure 1 in an predominantly angular manner. The fault is implemented by utilizing calibrated steel shims placed in the motor mountings and quantified by utilizing a commercial alignment tool. Table II shows the values of the implemented misalignment. The horizontal plane angle and offset are kept within acceptable limits.

TABLE II
VERTICAL MISALIGNMENT VALUES

	Misalignment lvl 1	Misalignment lvl 2
Vertical angle (θ)	0.442 °	0.704 °
Vertical off-set (d)	0.44 mm	0.79 mm

IV. TRANSIENT RADIAL VIBRATION SIGNATURE ANALYSIS

The present section analyses the radial vibration and current spectrum during directly-fed and soft-started start-ups. In addition, a transversal view among voltage, current, and vibration signals is provided. The time-frequency analysis of both current and radial vibration signals is performed by utilizing the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT). The STFT is a windowed version of the classic Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) which allows the identification of varying frequencies over time. It is defined by:

Fig. 4. Directly-fed machine start-up at reduced voltage, time domain signals, (a) phase-to-ground voltage, (b) phase current, (c) 12 o'clock vibration signal

Fig. 5. Soft-started machine start-up time domain signals, (a) phase-to-ground voltage in a controlled phase, (b) phase current in a controlled phase, (c) 12 o'clock vibration signal

$$STFT\{x(t)\} = X(\tau, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)w(t-\tau)e^{-2\pi fjt} dt \quad (1)$$

where $x(t)$ is the analysed discrete signal, and $w(t-\tau)$ represents the window function where τ symbolizes the location of the window function. Each signal segment is multiplied by a Hanning window prior FFT transformation in order to minimize spectral leakage.

Figures 4 and 5 show the directly-fed and soft-started time domain signals respectively at rated load (i.e., $s = 0.04$). The signals in the directly-fed mode reach steady-state in approximately 1 s, while the soft-started mode shows transient behaviour up to 20 s after the start, when the thyristor bridges are by-passed. The details in figure 5 show the effect of the thyristor bridges on the voltage and current, where the added distortion is clearly visible. Figure 4 shows a vibration signal with an initial shock followed by some small amplitude transients, while the soft-started vibration in figure 5 shows a more rich dynamic.

Fig. 6. Start-up time-frequency representation, 60% nominal voltage direct start-up (a) 12 o'clock radial vibration, (b) phase current, and soft-started start-up (c) 12 o'clock radial vibration, (d) phase current

Figure 6 shows the time-frequency representation via STFT for the healthy state for both current and radial vibration signals in the two starting modes. Figures 6 (a) and (b) show the directly-fed start-up for reduced voltage. The transient evolutions of different components are highlighted in the area ①. The initial mechanical shock blurs the evolution of the different time-evolving components since this kind of signal excites a broad frequency band. In the case of soft-started start-up (i.e., figures 6 (c) and (d)), different dynamic states are observed. The area ② is characterized by standstill rotor lock and only pure magnetic vibration is induced. The region ③ symbolizes the slow rotation, while in region ④ the rotor starts accelerating and the slip varies from nearly unitary to nominal value. The region ⑤ symbolizes the steady-state rotation with distorted voltage excitation. The thyristor bridges are bypassed once the region ⑤ is crossed.

The current signature in healthy state presents two main harmonic families added to the fundamental frequency. These are defined as Winding Harmonics (WH) and Principal Slot Harmonics (PSH) and are given by:

$$f_{WH} = f_s \nu \quad (2)$$

$$f_{PSH\pm} = f_s \left(\frac{R}{p} (1 - s) \pm \nu \right) \quad (3)$$

where f_s is the supply frequency, R is the number of rotor slots, p is the number of pole pairs and ν is an odd integer (i.e., $\nu = 1, 3, 5, \dots$). The comparison between soft-started and directly-fed currents supports past works such as [15], where higher amplitudes are observed in the WH of higher order (e.g., WH5, WH9, WH13, etc.). However, the analysis does not fully agree with [15] in the case of the PSH. In this case, a broader PSH content is observed in the current both in positive and negative families, while an increase of only negative sign PSH is reported in [15].

For vibration time-frequency plots in figures 6 (a) and (c), the directly-fed case shows little effect of even multiples

of twice line frequency components (i.e., νf_s where $\nu = 0, 2, 4, \dots$) while a strong contribution of these components is observed in the soft-started plot. High amplitude modulations at rotation frequency are observed around these components at $\nu f_s \pm k f_r \quad \forall \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ for low even values of ν . These represent the product of stator and rotor space harmonics [16]. Transient vibration signals include PSH families described by equation 3 with the only change of the parameter ν . In [17], the authors demonstrate that vibration PSH are defined by even values of ν . The soft-started transient shows increased number of positive PSH compared with the directly-fed start-up. Overall, the transient vibration in the directly-fed case offers little information compared with the soft-started case, which shows a rich spectrum of electromagnetic components.

V. MISALIGNMENT DEFECT ANALYSIS

A. Steady-state

The present subsection is aimed to the detailed analysis of misalignment indicators during steady-state at nominal conditions. On one hand, the rotating frequency side-bands around the fundamental harmonic $f_s \pm f_r$ represents a reliable and well-known indicator of misalignment and eccentricity in the current spectrum [4]. On the other hand the multiples of the rotating frequency are identified as indicators of misalignment in the vibration spectrum. Specifically, the significance of even multiples of the rotating frequency is usually more pronounced [1], [18]. In addition, the component $2f_s$ contains useful fault information. This component stems from the fundamental component of the air-gap flux density squared and is normally associated with airgap eccentricity or defects such as foot flatness, and frame and base stiffness [1].

Figure 7 shows the normalized current and 12 o'clock vibration spectrum for 4% slip and different misalignment levels. Note that vibration signals are not normalized with respect the fundamental component since resonance and damping heavily influences the signal amplitude. Tables III and IV

Fig. 7. Steady-state misalignment analysis, (a) Normalized phase current spectrum around f_s , (b) 12 o'clock vibration low frequency spectrum

show the amplitudes of potential fault indicators. The current spectrum $f_s \pm f_r$ clearly shows an amplitude increase for the misalignment cases. Nevertheless, the differences between the two misalignment levels are not significant and do not allow the effective discrimination. The vibration components show a marked difference in even multiples of the rotating frequency $2f_r, 4f_r$. The rotating frequency (i.e., $1 \times f_r$) does not provide reliable misalignment indication in this case. Nevertheless, the twice supply frequency component $2f_s$ is accentuated for increased misalignment levels.

TABLE III
PHASE CURRENT MISALIGNMENT INDICATORS

	$f_s - f_r$	$f_s + f_r$
Healthy (dB)	-53.91	-56.46
Misalignment lvl 1 (dB)	-45.46	-50.68
Misalignment lvl 2 (dB)	-46.16	-47.87

B. Soft-started start-up transient

The steady-state analysis of vibration provides misalignment indication but consequences and root locus of the defect cannot be properly addressed. To this aim, the slow soft-started transient vibration signal during the machine start-up is qualitatively analysed. Figure 8 shows the vibration transient evolutions for different levels of misalignment and

TABLE IV
12 O'CLOCK VIBRATION LOW FREQUENCY SPECTRUM MAIN COMPONENTS

	f_r	$2f_r$	$3f_r$	$4f_r$	$2f_s$
Healthy (dB)	-58.60	-74.28	-73.97	-79.79	-68.46
Misalignment lvl1 (dB)	-73.81	-64.39	-71.53	-63.21	-61.32
Misalignment lvl2 (dB)	-66.51	-54.90	-49.99	-50.17	-53.67

healthy conditions. The first phenomenon is observed during the PSH evolutions once the motor starts rotating. The slip evolves in a short period of time in the healthy case, while it decelerates for the misaligned cases. The second observation is the appearance of high amplitude broadband frequency content that blurs the transient evolutions of electromagnetic components such as PSH. For the first misalignment level, this shock is concentrated in time and coincides with the slip deceleration area. This effect is severe in the case of the second level of misalignment. Other causes for increased frequency spectrum for severe misalignment cases may stem from the flexible coupling inability to mitigate shaft irregularities thus, inducing some load related signature.

The main disadvantage of the evaluation of transient vibration during the start-up lays on the difficulty to define quantitative fault indicators. Time-frequency maps consist of normalized amplitude pixels and thus, mechanical irregularities (i.e., load induced components, contacts, etc.) induce a high amplitude signature that obstructs the identification of significant fault components. Another uncertainty stems from unwanted contacts and light changes on the mechanical system. These may alter the vibration response of the system, inducing instantaneous structural resonance or damping [13]. Nevertheless, evident differences are observed for different levels of misalignment in figure 8, mostly related to slip-dependent electromagnetic signature evolutions and the presence of wide frequency bandwidth forces. In addition, the effect of the load related signature is clearly observed, which induces high amplitude multiples of the rotating frequency in figure 8 (c).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The present manuscript explores the utilization of transient radial vibration signals during the machine start-up to enhance the reliability of misalignment detection. The main theoretical concepts behind electrical machine vibration and misalignment are briefly reviewed to enhance the comprehensibility of the work. A 1.1 kW induction motor test bench is utilized to test the proposed technique. Note that fast start-ups produce in initial vibration shock that blur the signal components with physical information (e.g., PSH or rotation frequencies). For this reason, slow soft-started transient is implemented by utilizing thyristor bridges. The differences between directly-fed and soft-started start-ups are thoroughly analysed to elucidate the current and vibration signature in healthy state. The misalignment is implemented in two degrees of severity. The steady-state analysis of well-known current and vibra-

Fig. 8. Transient soft-started 12 o'clock vibration signal in nominal conditions, (a) healthy, (b) misalignment lvl 1, (c) misalignment lvl 2

tion fault indicators elucidate the presence of misalignment, differentiating in some cases between severity levels. The transient analysis provides qualitative information in terms of electromagnetic component evolutions and energy distribution during the start-up. The presence of wide frequency bandwidth forces is evident in the severe misalignment case, while extremely localized in time for lighter misalignment. Nevertheless, slip dependent transient evolutions irregularly evolve for both misalignment levels. This qualitative analysis is interesting for machines with intermittent operation, where steady-state signals may not provide conclusive information about severity and root locus of the fault. Future work includes the experimentation with supply frequency variations (i.e., inverter-fed start-up) and directly-fed machines with large inertia and long start-up times.

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